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Methodological approaches and managerial insights in supply chain stress testing

Hiran Prathapage, Dmitry Ivanov^{1*}

Berlin School of Economics and Law, Department of Business Administration

Professor for Supply Chain and Operations Management, 10825 Berlin, Germany

Phone: +49 308771155; E-Mail: divanov@hwr-berlin.de

** Corresponding author E-Mail: divanov@hwr-berlin.de*

Abstract

Supply chains are constantly stressed by various internal and external disruption events. The COVID-19 pandemic, geopolitical tensions, and natural hazards have highlighted the critical importance of maintaining resilience and viable capabilities to ensure business continuity. Recently introduced stress tests in supply chain management (SCM) have the ability to analyze, predict, and recommend recovery plans to stay competitive. In this paper, we analyzed the progress of stress tests and their applications. We applied the bibliometric analysis approach to find new topics, methods, and different disruptions analyzed employing stress tests. We defined the stress test in relation to SCM and categorized it based on its application. Our bibliometric analysis reveals recent conceptual and technological advancements that can aid in assessing the resilience level of supply chain networks. In particular, we described the significance of collaborations, viability, data analytics, and artificial intelligence (AI) with respect to stress testing. Theoretical and managerial implications with several future research directions were elaborated to conclude this paper.

Keywords: Supply chain resilience, ripple effect, stress test, resilience, viability, analytics

SDG 9: Industry, innovation and infrastructure

1. Introduction

Supply chain resilience (SCR) has received significant attention from both academia and industry alike, following the unprecedented disruptions caused by the COVID-19 pandemic (Ivanov and Dolgui 2021a, Sawik 2022, Brintrup et al. 2023). Unexpected lockdowns, unpredictable demand fluctuations, and the contagious nature of the virus collectively propagated the impact (i.e., ripple effect), jeopardizing the efficiency and performance of supply chain networks. Even though the ripple effect was sufficiently studied before 2019 (Sokolov et al. 2015, Ivanov 2017a, Ivanov et al. 2017b, Ojha et al. 2018), no supply chain could survive the unexpected constant stress placed by the pandemic. Some supply chains collapsed while others barely survived. This compelled practitioners to reconsider their level of preparedness for disruptions, aiming to enhance both survivability (i.e. “ability to continue to exist and secure the provision of society with vital needs”) (Ivanov, 2021a p. 135) and adaptability (Ivanov 2022) in the long run. Stress tests can be integrated with decision support systems to analyze inconsistencies in supply chain networks proactively and reactively.

Stress tests have been used in different disciplines to evaluate the impact of different scenarios. In medicine, stress tests are employed to check the overall or specific health of patients. Required data is collected and analyzed while patients perform various activities (Nalesso et al. 2024). In financial sector, potential impacts on assets and liabilities due to events and movements are checked using stress tests (Rhee and Dogra 2023). In material science, stress tests can be used to examine the durability of the materials when they are stressed (Winzer et al. 2008). In SCM, stress tests are mainly discussed in relation to resilience analyses. Simchi-Levi and Simchi-Levi (2020) introduced the term “stress test” in the context of SCM while emphasizing its importance for critical supply chains, during the COVID-19 pandemic. Since then, stress tests have been consistently employed to conduct resilience analyses across various crisis scenarios.

The pandemic and post-pandemic period have been exacerbated by a range of emerging global tensions, including economic instabilities, geopolitical conflicts, semiconductor shortages, and natural hazards. This provided supply chain managers with an opportunity to evaluate the robustness of their networks. Meanwhile, the primary concern raised among SCR scholars during and after the pandemic is the extent to which resilience capabilities should be integrated into the system to ensure survivability and adaptability (Hosseini and Ivanov 2021). Additionally, although the likelihood of another pandemic-like disruption is high, should we also prepare the supply chain for another macro-scale disruption, such as climate change (Bag, 2022)? Such rational decisions are inherently difficult to make due to the complexity involved. Furthermore, resilience is not a collection of capabilities that comes without cost. Incorporating multiple suppliers incurs costs associated with managing the processes of selection, assessment, integration, and development (Ivanov et al. 2021 p. 126-127). Stock redundancies can increase the carrying and obsolescence costs. Therefore, such trade-offs should be carefully analyzed to optimize the resilience effort without injecting extra burdens to the cash flow. Stress tests can be utilized to analyze disruption scenarios across various extremes and generate comparable analytics to evaluate the associated key performance indicators (KPIs) (Ivanov and Dolgui 2021a, Ivanov 2023a).

Although several SCM studies have referenced the term "stress test" and incorporated it into their analyses (Ivanov and Dolgui 2021a, Ivanov 2023a) a comprehensive explanation of its definition and applications remains insufficiently addressed in the literature. Moreover, we are not aware of any available publication that systematically analyzes the evolution and application of stress testing within the field of SCM.

In light of this research gap, we undertake this study to address the following three research questions descriptively:

***RQ1:** What is a stress test in supply chain management and why is it useful?*

***RQ2:** How has the supply chain stress testing progressed with regard to major topics and applied methodologies?*

***RQ3:** What are the expected future research directions in the area of supply chain stress tests?*

Our contribution to the literature involves analyzing stress test-related studies conducted before and after the COVID-19 pandemic, benchmarking the surge in resilience-focused research.

Bibliometric methodology is used to identify major topic interests of researchers and common methodologies applied to conduct stress tests. The nature of disruptions considered is analyzed with respect to pre- and post-2019 periods to identify shifts in focus and direction. Subsequently, the application of stress tests to make decisions is elaborated from the practitioners' point of view.

Our major findings can be summarized as follows. We analyzed the application of stress tests in different disciplines and defined the term with respect to SCM. Major topics with promising research directions are recognized subsequently. We categorized stress tests into two branches based on their applications and proposed a framework for conducting stress tests using digital twin. Managerial implications and future research directions are derived at the end.

The remainder of the paper is organized as follows. Section 2 presents the bibliometric methodology and its results. Section 3 elaborates on the findings from the literature analysis. In Section 4, theoretical and managerial implications, along with future research areas, are discussed. Finally, Section 5 provides the conclusion.

2. Review methodology and the scope

The literature review methodology has been widely employed as a traditional approach to analyzing existing knowledge across various disciplines. Defined and tested by leading researchers, literature review is an efficient technique integrated with a set of common guidelines to study and summarize the existing knowledge and generate new research directions (Queiroz et al. 2020). In this paper, we employed the traditional literature review approach to understand the current knowledge related to stress test in SCM. An iterative process of selecting and defining relevant keywords, filtering the results to get a reasonable sample, analyzing the literature, summarizing the results and generating the new research directions is used in this review.

The term "stress test" is relatively new in the field of SCM, despite its popularity in other disciplines. Therefore, to look for more related keywords that have been paired with stress test, we started the analysis with a simple search string (i.e. ("supply chain" OR "supply network") AND ("stress test*" OR "stress-test*")) and limited the subject areas to Engineering, Business, management and Accounting, Computer Science and Decision Science. Proofing our assumption, only 42 articles were prompted as illustrated in Fig. 1. Scanning through the abstracts, running the VOS Viewer analysis and fine-tuning by the experts in the area, we collected important keywords to run our extended search string.

The below extended search string is used for further analysis of the literature review.

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(( TITLE-ABS-KEY ( "supply chain" ) OR TITLE-ABS-KEY ( "supply network" ) AND TITLE-ABS-KEY ( "resilience" ) OR TITLE-ABS-KEY ( "disruption" ) AND TITLE-ABS-KEY ( "predict*" ) OR TITLE-ABS-KEY ( "ripple effect" ) OR TITLE-ABS-KEY ( "performance impact" ) OR TITLE-ABS-KEY ( "stress test*" ) OR TITLE-ABS-KEY ( "stress-test*" ) ) ) AND ( LIMIT-TO ( EXACTSRCTITLE , "International Journal Of Production Research" ) OR LIMIT-TO ( EXACTSRCTITLE , "Computers And Industrial Engineering" ) OR LIMIT-TO ( EXACTSRCTITLE , "International Journal Of Production Economics" ) OR LIMIT-TO ( EXACTSRCTITLE , "Annals Of Operations Research" ) OR LIMIT-TO (
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EXACTSRCTITLE , "Transportation Research Part E Logistics And Transportation Review") OR LIMIT-TO (EXACTSRCTITLE , "International Journal Of Operations And Production Management") OR LIMIT-TO (EXACTSRCTITLE , "IEEE Transactions On Engineering Management") OR LIMIT-TO (EXACTSRCTITLE , "Production And Operations Management") OR LIMIT-TO (EXACTSRCTITLE , "European Journal Of Operational Research") OR LIMIT-TO (EXACTSRCTITLE , "International Journal Of Physical Distribution And Logistics Management") OR LIMIT-TO (EXACTSRCTITLE , "Journal Of Supply Chain Management") OR LIMIT-TO (EXACTSRCTITLE , "Journal Of Business Logistics") OR LIMIT-TO (EXACTSRCTITLE , "Journal Of Operations Management") OR LIMIT-TO (EXACTSRCTITLE , "Journal Of Purchasing And Supply Management") OR LIMIT-TO (EXACTSRCTITLE , "Journal Of Business Research") OR LIMIT-TO (EXACTSRCTITLE , "Computers And Operations Research") OR LIMIT-TO (EXACTSRCTITLE , "Operational Research") OR LIMIT-TO (EXACTSRCTITLE , "Manufacturing And Service Operations Management") OR LIMIT-TO (EXACTSRCTITLE , "Transportation Research Part B Methodological") OR LIMIT-TO (EXACTSRCTITLE , "Decision Sciences") OR LIMIT-TO (EXACTSRCTITLE , "Management Science") OR LIMIT-TO (EXACTSRCTITLE , "Iise Transactions") OR LIMIT-TO (EXACTSRCTITLE , "Journal Of The Operational Research Society") OR LIMIT-TO (EXACTSRCTITLE , "Operations Research") OR LIMIT-TO (EXACTSRCTITLE , "Decision Support Systems") OR LIMIT-TO (EXACTSRCTITLE , "Omega United Kingdom") OR LIMIT-TO (EXACTSRCTITLE , "International Journal Of Logistics Management") OR LIMIT-TO (EXACTSRCTITLE , "International Journal Of Integrated Supply Management"))

Fig. 1. The flowchart of the literature review methodology

test*" in the SCOPUS database reveals that, of the 25,775 articles retrieved, 15,728 (approximately 61%) are published within the medicine stream. In these studies, stress testing is regarded as a technique for measuring variations by altering the existing nature of the system. For instance, Nalesso et al. (2024) explained that stress testing techniques such as protein loading, and pharmacological stimuli can be used to assess the renal functional reserve variations in living kidney donors. According to social science stress theories, stress can arise as a reaction (i.e. physique), as a stimulus, or as a transaction (i.e. psyche) to external changes (Céline and Peter 2023). The stress test has become a key tool in the financial sector, particularly during the global financial crises in 2007-2009. Rhee and Dogra (2023) mentioned that stress tests can restore the confidence in the financial system by analyzing associated risks during a crisis and providing credible predictions. However, they argued that such tests cannot provide information with perfect accuracy as they inevitably ignore some risk sources that can change the system completely. For further details, we refer to the research conducted by Linkov et al. (2022).

Stress test was adapted to the SCM stream to assess the SCR and viability particularly during and after the COVID-19 pandemic (Ivanov 2023a, Ivanov and Dolgui 2021a), following its successful application in other disciplines. Subsequently, stress tests have also been employed to explore bottlenecks that emerge within the supply chain network (Alikhani et al. 2021). Moreover, stress tests are evidently employed to examine supply chain shocks, including supplier disruptions (Trkman and McCormack 2009, Hosseini et al. 2019, Padhi and Mukherjee 2022), demand disruptions (Ivanov 2021b, Badakhshan and Ball 2022), and disruption propagation (Ojha et al. 2018, Hosseini and Ivanov 2022). However, Ivanov and Dolgui (2021a) argued that both positive (“government initiatives supporting sustainable manufacturing, business-driven digital technology”...) and negative (“pandemics, financial crises, climate change”...) stressors can coexist and be analyzed through stress testing.

3.2. *Major topics*

In order to examine the major topics discussed in the literature, a co-occurrence analysis using VOS Viewer software is conducted. The software can be employed to collect co-occurrence data with detailed clustered illustrations (Appendix 1). Fig. 3 illustrates the extracted co-occurrence data generated using VOS Viewer software, highlighting the major topics discussed, particularly during and after the COVID-19 pandemic. This period marks a critical transformation point in the context of stress testing.

We ran the analysis for the period of 2004-2024. The threshold was set as “at least 5 times co-occurred” to obtain the results. Irrelevant keywords were unselected to increase the quality and the relationships of the output. In Fig. 3, the green series shows the average publication year of the articles, in which the corresponding keyword is used. Moreover, if a term is continuously used or recently introduced, the average publication year increases. The orange series represents the average number of citations received by the articles in which the respective keyword appeared. The low average number of citations signals the novelty of the topics, as they receive fewer citations despite being published in leading journals. We considered 2021 as the benchmark to find the most significant and recent topics. Keywords included in the SCOPUS search string were deliberately less prioritized, as they are more likely to appear in the list. The keywords are then validated with detailed reading. A detailed overview of keyword analysis can be found in Appendix 2.

Fig. 3. Keyword analysis

The identified keywords are classified and discussed in detail below. Major topics selected are categorized under concepts, performance analysis, and technologies in Table 1, along with several indicative references.

Table 1. Stress test related taxonomies

Topics accompanied by stress test		Indicative references
Major concepts	Collaboration	(Giannoccaro and Iftikhar 2020), (Ivanov 2022), (Küffner et al. 2022)
	COVID-19	(Hosseini and Ivanov, 2021), (Moosavi and Hosseini 2021), (Sawik 2023a)
	Supply chain risks and uncertainty	(Ivanov et al. 2016c), (Paul et al. 2017), (Hosseini et al. 2019)
	Viability	(Ivanov 2022), (Sawik 2023a)
Performance analysis	Big data analytics	(Bag et al. 2022)
	Predictive analytics	(Paul et al. 2017), (Bag et al. 2022)
	Decision support systems	(Ivanov et al. 2018)
Technologies	Artificial intelligence	(Brintrup et al. 2023)
	Machine learning	(Badakhshan and Ball 2022)

Collaboration

Having received 2021.71 as the average publication year and 23.28 as the average citation count, the supply chain collaboration can be interpreted as a novel topic that is discussed in relation to stress test. Supply chain collaboration is applied as a resilience and viability capability in several recent studies. Using discrete-event simulation (DES) approach, Ivanov (2023b) examined the impact of collaborative intertwined supply networks on ripple effect

while considering supplier disruption as the stressor. During the disruption period, the inventory can be shared among networked manufacturers. Additionally, two alternative backup plans (i.e. capacity re-purposing and usage of substitute materials) can be implemented as required. He concluded that applying these capabilities could mitigate the ripple effect and improve the existing performance subject to reaction delays. Giannoccaro and Iftikhar (2020) conducted a similar experiment using agent-based modeling. They conducted the influence of trust between the collaborative network and their topology on SCR. Measuring the resilience at different network performance levels, they summarized that information sharing and collaboration among partners can improve the resilience of the network according to a dynamic perspective. In the study of Küffner et al. (2022), the importance of the internal and external collaboration at purchasing and supply disruptions was analyzed using the qualitative survey approach. They emphasized that internal stakeholder collaborations as an initial measure upon the occurrence of the disruption and external collaborations (i.e. leveraging established and trusted relationships) as a temporary measure during the disruption play a pivotal role in improving the resilience. The conceptual paper developed by Ivanov (2022) further explained that such collaborations could even occur between different ecosystems and share common resources.

COVID-19 pandemic

How a single disruptive event, followed by unexpected localized sub-events, can decimate a well-planned supply chain network was clearly demonstrated during the COVID-19 pandemic and has captured significant attention from researchers. However, the stress an epidemic outbreak can inject was accurately predicted and analyzed by Ivanov (2020) well before the COVID-19 pandemic was officially announced. Employing the DES approach, he demonstrated how a series of unexpected events could lead to disruption propagation. The paper clearly showed the short-term and long-term consequences in terms of production-inventory fluctuations, service level, and financial and lead-time performance. The remedies suggested by Ivanov (2020) were analyzed in detail by others, both during and after the pandemic. For instance, Badakhshan and Ball (2022) analyzed the impact of pandemic-like events on supply chain performance using a combination of simulation and machine learning (ML). In their digital twin framework, DES generates inventory and cash replenishment data following disruptions, which is subsequently fed into the ML model to derive new decision rules. Motivated by the pandemic, Sawik (2023a) also developed a stochastic optimization model that considers two conflicting objectives, cost and customer service level, allowing decision-makers to select their own viable production strategies. He concluded that greater distance between boundary trajectories enhances viability and resilience under ripple effect. Conducting semi-structured interviews, Raassens et al. (2021) empirically analyzed different crisis management strategies that can be trained by previous long-term disruptions to prepare the supply chain for future events. They suggested that resource management, resource dependency, collaboration, and effective communication can mitigate the stress arising from long-term disruptions. Three distinguishable stages can be identified in studies of the COVID-19 pandemic (Ivanov, 2024), regardless of whether they employ quantitative or qualitative methodologies.

- Impact prediction stage – Stressed by early signals of demand fluctuations and supplier disruptions.

- Impact-facing stage – stressed by internal factors such as unpredictable supply, demand, financial and logistics disruptions, and external factors such as lockdowns, government rules, and regulations.
- Exiting stage – stressed by continuity of adapted strategies during the impact-facing stage (e.g. capacity redundancies, collaborations, and repurposing)

Supply chain risks and uncertainty

Supply chain risks and uncertainties are primary stages of disruptions (Ivanov 2021a p. 4), providing decision-makers with the necessary early warnings to plan potential mitigation strategies for dynamic changes. In fact, disruptions, COVID-19, resilience, viability and mitigation strategies have evolved around risks and uncertainties. Supply chain risks are two-folded, i.e. operational (uncertainties that emerged due to “everyday” events with high occurrence frequency) and disruption (disruptive events such as “natural disasters, human-made threats, or employee strikes” with low occurrence frequency) (Hosseini et al. 2019, Ivanov 2021a p. 10). Employing a heuristic approach, Paul et al. (2017) developed a reactive mitigation plan to address frequent changes in production systems caused by technical and internal risks. Liu and Ren (2024) also studied frequent production disruptions arising from labor strikes, natural disasters or equipment breakdown using the mean-variance method. Therefore, it is evident that certain risks occur more frequently in specific supply chains than in others. Detailed analysis of different disruptions studied is discussed under 3.4.

Viability

Based on the average publication year (2022.33) and the average citation count (38), viability emerges as a relatively novel concept, introduced in response to the COVID-19 pandemic and its ripple effect. The concept is understood as the expanded iteration of the concept of resilience (Ivanov 2022, Sawik 2023a). Sawik (2023a) distinguished resilience and viability according to the severity of the disruption (i.e. moderate vs crisis). He proposed a stochastic quadratic optimization model for viability incorporating backup suppliers, capacity reservations, and pre-positioned risk inventory as viable mitigation strategies. In this analysis, the disruption was triggered by a pandemic-like event, geographically dispersed, thereby creating ripple effect. He concluded that higher distance between boundary trajectories (i.e. cost-optimal and service-optimal) increases the viability and resilience under ripple effect. In his conceptual paper, Ivanov (2022) described viability as a survival-oriented, long-term strategy designed to address changing environments. He emphasized that most supply chains intersect with one another, and to ensure the viability of the network, structural redesigns and process adaptations should be introduced.

As shown in Table 2, disruption events can be categorized into three distinct types from the perspective of viability. Short-term events, such as floods and fires, exhibit seasonal patterns and can be predicted (Gunessee et al. 2018, Bag et al. 2022). The scenario data generated by past events can be integrated with stress tests to simulate and predict the impact, and prepare the supply chain to close the loop by bouncing back (i.e. resilience). Medium and long-term events are hard to predict (Sakib et al. 2021, Gunessee et al. 2018). They are called unknown-unknown uncertainties (i.e. unknown disruption events and unknown impact) (Ivanov 2024). This uncertainty can introduce significant stress to the system, requiring the supply chain to

develop viable capabilities for adaptation (e.g. material repurposing). The medium-term viability perspective acts as an “extension of SCR toward survivability under super disruptions” and in the long-term “the viable supply chain encompasses resilience, sustainability, and leagility (i.e. leanness and agility)” (Ivanov, 2021a p. 135) of the entire ecosystem. Situational adaptations and multi-structural intertwined network transformations are imperative in the long run.

Table 2. Viability perspectives (adopted with changes from Ivanov, 2021a p. 142)

Time horizon	Predictability	Stress level	Examples	Strategies	Suitable concept
Short-term	High	Low	Flood, Fire	Recovery and firm’s resilience	Resilience
Medium-term	Low	High	Pandemic	Adaptation and supply chain survivability	Viability
Long-term	Low	High	Climate change, poverty	Adaptation and multi-structural network transformation	Viability

Big data, predictive analytics and decision support systems

Cyber supply chain networks continuously generate various types of data (e.g. sales data, logistics data, manufacturing data, and material supply data), which can be utilized for analysis, modeling, and control (Ivanov et al. 2018). Supply chain risks, on the other hand, provide essential data for stress testing, which can subsequently be used to produce more accurate predictions (Ivanov 2023a). For instance, Bag et al. (2022) developed a model to enhance supply chain visibility and the final effects on community and resource resilience by accurate predictions using extreme weather event data in advance. Following a comprehensive analysis of in-depth interviews and survey data, they concluded that big data and predictive analytics improve the ability to manage available resources more efficiently during disruptions. Paul et al. (2017) developed two use cases of big data and predictive analytics. Firstly, a predictive mitigation plan was developed based on the changes in forecasted demand data due to unexpected and natural incidents. Secondly, a reactive mitigation plan was proposed considering sudden changes in production systems data due to technical and internal problems. In-depth literature analyses of various big data and predictive analytics use cases (Kumar et al. 2023, Jahani et al. 2023, Smyth et al. 2024) show the potential applications and future research directions for improving SCR.

Data analytics forms the foundation for decision support systems. Supply chains are interconnected systems, inherently built upon complex relationships (Hilletoft and Lättilä 2012, Ivanov et al. 2018). Therefore, systems capable of analyzing both structured and unstructured data, and interpreting their logical connections, are required. Ivanov et al. (2018) argued that decision support systems for risk analytics and stress testing should focus on proactive resilience and structural-parametrical adaptation (i.e. viability). They concluded by

proposing a comprehensive framework that integrates optimization, simulation, and data analytics methods to assist decision-makers in addressing resilience and viability related issues. Stress test is a part of the optimization and simulation methods and acts as the brain of risk focused decision support systems which defines the network capabilities at extreme conditions.

Artificial intelligence and machine learning

AI is emerging as one of the leading data-driven technologies for decision-making, due to its “interoperability, data storage, and business analytics capabilities” (Sharma et al. 2022). In the supply chain domain, AI techniques are typically studied in conjunction with optimization or probability theory and mathematical statistics methods. Ortiz-Barrios et al. (2023) developed a framework to predict the likelihood of patients requiring treatments in a pandemic-like event and used that data to simulate the demand of health systems. In the first phase, they predicted the probability of a patient ending up in the intensive care unit using *random forest* technique. The predicted data was then simulated using *DES* to upgrade the intensive bed inventory management system. They concluded that such a mixed-methods approach could significantly reduce patients’ waiting time. Babazadeh et al. (2024) employed a hybrid of *artificial neural networks* and *mathematical programming* methods to mitigate disruptions in production planning. Firstly, the demand and its peak points were predicted using neural networks. Secondly, the predicted demand data was integrated with a multi-objective agile recovery production planning model to optimize the production and distribution activities. They concurred with the conclusions drawn by Ortiz-Barrios et al. (2023).

ML represents a primary subfield of AI, with techniques such as random forests and neural networks classified as specific methodologies within ML. Numerous other ML techniques are widely recognized and utilized by researchers in the field of SCM. Zheng et al. (2023) highlighted the limitations inherent in risk prediction models centered on individual organizations and introduced a collective risk prediction framework, employing *federated machine learning* to enhance predictive accuracy. Badakhshan and Ball (2022) developed a model to assess the effects of disruptions in both physical and financial flows on supply chain dynamics, employing the Classification and Regression Tree (CART) algorithm within a *decision tree* framework. ML offers several advantages that enhance its ability to support stress testing in SCM (Ni et al. 2019).

1. Ability to describe non-linear relationships.
2. Ability to deal with unstructured data sets.
3. Suitability as a better performance prediction tool.
4. Ability to explore potential applications in the maintenance of physical assets and physical inspection.

3.3. Methodologies of supply chain stress testing

There are numerous methods applied in the literature to conduct stress tests. Supply chain analytical approaches can be broadly classified into two main categories: optimization methods and simulation methods, each encompassing several subcategories. These methods are extensively applied in modelling research to analyze the system behavior when stressed. Empirical research approaches can also be utilized to understand the impact of stressed supply chain networks to generate useful insights. Table 3 provides a summary of the various

methodologies applied in the selected sample for conducting respective studies. The count of methods is higher than the number of studies selected due to the mixed approach considered in some papers.

Table 3. Methodological approaches for stress testing

Research type	Methodology	Number of studies
Modelling research	Discrete-Event Simulation	7
	Bayesian Networks	5
	Stochastic Optimization	5
	Linear/Mixed-Integer Programming	3
	System Dynamics	3
	Fuzzy Theory	3
	Graph Theory	2
	Others	7
Empirical research	Survey	7
	Case-Study	1
	Experimental Research	1
Conceptual papers	Case-Study	4

Stress test in modelling research

Having applied in seven studies, DES is the most used approach in modelling research. DES is identified as an effective method to capture the inherent complexities of supply chain networks by many researchers and practitioners (Moosavi and Hosseini 2021). Simulation methods in general have the capability of handling randomness and DES in particular can be employed to understand how a system reacts over time and compare its performance under different conditions (Park et al. 2021). Areas such as supply chain structure, replenishment control policies, supply chain optimization, and disruptions are some of the examples where DES can be employed. In our selected sample, all studies that utilized DES analyzed supply chain performance in relation to the "ripple effect". Even before the COVID-19 pandemic, Ivanov et al. (2016c), Ivanov (2017a), and Ivanov (2017b) showed the capability of using the DES method to analyze the disruption propagation, which was particularly useful during and after the pandemic period for practitioners to observe the disruption propagation. Further, Moosavi and Hosseini (2021), Badakhshan and Ball (2022), and Ivanov (2021b) employed the DES in relation to the COVID-19 pandemic. The study of disruption propagation in a complex circular flow by Park et al. (2021) shows the versatility of DES application. Bayesian Networks is also a popular method, particularly among researchers who are studying disruption propagation in complex networks due to its ability to handle complexity and uncertainty. Unlike other similar approaches, "the Bayes theorem" explicitly represents the "conditional probability dependencies between different variables through feedback" (Ojha et al. 2018). Aligned with DES, the ripple effect is also a central topic (Ojha et al. 2018, Hosseini and Ivanov 2021, Hosseini and Ivanov 2022, Liu et al. 2024) studied in relation to Bayesian networks.

Among others, stochastic optimization and linear/mixed-integer programming are the major optimization methods used for stress testing. Mathematical optimization methods are particularly useful for finding optimal solutions to complex supply chain problems. Mathematical optimization models are twofold, depending on the data with which they are integrated. In *uncertain* models, some of the parameters are considered to be unknown or stochastic (Mula et al. 2010). These models can handle the uncertainty involved in most of the complex supply chain problems. Stochastic optimization is one such model considered by Dixit et al. (2016), Hosseini et al. (2019), Sawik (2022), Sawik (2023a), and Sawik (2023b) to conduct their studies. In *deterministic* models, all the parameters are considered to be known. Linear/mixed-integer programming is a subset of deterministic models, which is employed by Ivanov et al. (2014), Ivanov et al. (2016a), and Ivanov et al. (2017b). In the latter two studies, these linear programming models were combined with the system dynamics method, which is categorized under *dynamical system theory* and enables the integration of both optimization and simulation approaches. Apart from that, Ghadge et al. (2021) also employ the system dynamic approach. Additionally, fuzzy theory (Paul et al. 2017, Pavlov et al. 2018, López and Ishizaka 2019), and graph theory (Ivanov et al. 2016b, Sokolov et al. 2015) were also applied under modelling research. A detailed explanation of other methods used can be found in Appendix 3.

Stress test in empirical research and conceptual papers

Often optimization and simulation methods are developed subject to assumptions in order to reduce the complexity. However, this may hinder capturing the effects of real-life complexities, which can considerably change the scenario (Chandrasekaran et al. 2018). Supply chains can be disrupted due to issues that are qualitative in nature. Empirical research methods such as experimental research, surveys, and case studies have the ability to capture qualitative characteristics. Surveys and case-study methods are more popular among SCM researchers. In the survey method, data is collected from primary sources using questionnaires or interviews from a large number of respondents to capture the maximum possible variabilities. Seven studies (Bode and Wagner 2015, Raassens et al. 2021, Padhi and Mukherjee 2022, Küffner et al. 2022, Bag et al. 2022, Brintrup et al. 2023, Padhi et al. 2024) considered this approach to conduct their studies and in addition to survey method, Brintrup et al. (2023) combined the study with a case to improve the reliability of the analysis. Moreover, Gunesssee et al. (2018) employed the quasi-experiment method to analyze the effect of two disaster events on end assemblers' performance in relation to the personal computer supply chain. The considered four conceptual papers (Trkman and McCormack 2009, Ivanov et al. 2018, Ivanov 2022, Ambrogio et al. 2022) show the significance of SCR and propose new frameworks with explanatory use cases.

3.4. Shifts in disruption analyses

The COVID-19 pandemic was a wake-up call for most businesses to rethink their risk mitigation strategies and it emphasized how peculiar an event can behave. Relatively stable supply and demand, well-managed risks and uncertainty, long-term planning, and lean-oriented network structures could not handle the stress placed by the unprecedented disruption (Ivanov 2021b). Consequently, researchers also shifted the focus to analyze system dynamics in relation to long-term cascading disruptions triggered by COVID-19. Table 4 shows the different disruption areas studied before and after the pandemic period.

Table 4. Analysis of disruptions before and after COVID-19

Time period	Reference	Disruption type							
		S	M&P	DC	MF	D	L	F	O
Until 2019 (Before COVID-19)	(Trkman and McCormack, 2009)	√							
	(Mizgier et al., 2013)	√							
	(Ivanov et al., 2014)				√				
	(Sokolov et al., 2015)				√				
	(Bode and Wagner, 2015)	√							
	(Dixit et al., 2016)								√
	(Ivanov et al., 2016a)				√				
	(Ivanov et al., 2016b)	√							
	(Ivanov et al., 2016c)			√					
	(Ivanov, 2017a)			√					
	(Ivanov, 2017b)			√					
	(Ivanov et al., 2017a)				√				
	(Ivanov et al., 2017b)				√				
	(Paul et al., 2017)		√						
	(Ojha et al., 2018)				√				
	(Gunessee et al., 2018)	√	√						
	(Pavlov et al., 2018)				√				
	(Wang et al., 2018)	√	√			√			
	(Rahmani and Yavari, 2019)					√			
	(López and Ishizaka, 2019)								√
(Hosseini et al., 2019)	√								
Total		7	3	3	7	2	0	0	2
	(Giannoccaro and Iftikhar, 2020)				√				
	(Ghadge et al., 2021)	√				√	√		
	(Park et al., 2021)		√						
	(Moosavi and Hosseini, 2021)	√	√						
	(Sakib et al., 2021)								√
	(Hosseini and Ivanov, 2021)		√				√		
	(Ivanov, 2021b)					√			
	(Padhi and Mukherjee, 2022)	√							
	(Badakhshan and Ball, 2022)		√			√		√	
	(Ambrogio et al., 2022)								√
	(Hosseini and Ivanov, 2022)	√							
	(Küffner et al., 2022)	√							
	(Sawik, 2022)	√	√			√			
	(Sawik, 2023a)	√				√			
	(Sawik, 2023b)	√	√			√	√		
	(Liu & Ren, 2024)		√						
(Liu et al., 2024)	√								
Total		9	7	0	1	6	3	1	2

Heading: “S”= Supplier; “M&P”= Manufacturing and Production; “DC”= Distribution Center; “MF”= Multi-Facilities; “D”= Demand; “L”= Logistics; “F”= Financial; “O”= Others

While the interest in supplier disruptions, manufacturing and production disruptions, demand disruptions, logistics disruptions, and financial disruptions continue to increase, disruptions related to distribution centers are less prioritized. Multi-facility disruptions where disruption propagation is considered show a significant drop after the pandemic. However, ripple effect studies are continuously emerging while being more specific on where and how the disruption propagation occurs. For instance, Ghadge et al. (2021) examine the disruption propagation subject to supply, logistics, and demand risks and their simultaneous existence. Similarly, Sawik (2022) studied the ripple effect assuming the disruption risk impact only on primary and backup suppliers, original equipment manufacturers, and market demand.

4. Theoretical and managerial implications

This section provides an in-depth examination of the theoretical and managerial implications associated with stress test. Despite the extensive development of stress test-related methods, analyses, and frameworks by scholars, a precise and universally accepted definition remains absent in the supply chain and operations management literature. Accordingly, this section begins by proposing a comprehensive definition of stress testing, followed by a framework aimed at facilitating its practical application.

4.1. Defining the stress test

Stress tests have been used in many disciplines including medicine, engineering, and finance to study the behavior of complex systems. During the COVID-19 pandemic, Simchi-Levi and Simchi-Levi (2020) first introduced the term “stress test” to the SCM discipline by publishing a seminal paper entitled ‘We Need a Stress Test for Critical Supply Chains’. They emphasized the intricacies involved in the analyses of critical supply chain networks during a super disruption. Motivated by this direction and the definitions of other disciplines discussed in section 3.1, we define the stress test in relation to SCM as follows. Fig. 4 further explains the application of stress test.

“A test that can be used to observe dynamical variations of a system in a real environment or in a virtual environment by altering existing conditions to prepare the network with accurate predictions”.

Fig. 4. Application of stress tests

Stress test can be simulated in an actual environment or a virtual environment. Selecting a specific area according to the focus of the study and experimenting with it in a controlled setting/environment facilitates examiners to obtain a clear picture of a real system without disrupting the running processes. The method is extensively employed in other disciplines to examine disruption scenarios. For instance, Chen et al. (2013) created a Tsunami in a controlled environment (i.e. a glass-walled wave flume in a hydraulics laboratory) to assess the potential damage to the coastal road system which helps to better plan the disaster relief. This approach can also be applied to solve SCM issues (Perera and Fahimnia 2024). However, the actual behavior of subjective factors, such as the behavior of supply chain actors, may not be accurately captured within a controlled environment. Such scenarios should be conducted in a real setting/environment. Those laboratory and field experiments in real environments are pioneer approaches in empirical studies. However, due to the high costs involved in laboratory experiments and the improvements of digitalization, most of the stress tests are conducted as digital lab experiments in virtual environments. Stress tests are twofold in virtual settings; i.e. optimization and simulation. While optimization methods are utilized to find optimal solutions, simulation methods are useful to observe the supply chain dynamics according to the rules defined by the modeler. These methods are extensively used in modelling research. Table 5 helps to distinguish the methods described.

Table 5. Stress test in real environment vs. virtual environment

Criterion	Stress test in real-environment	Stress test in virtual environment
Run-time	Long and time consuming	Adjustable and less time consuming
Cost	Relatively expensive	Economical
Ability	Some scenarios are expensive or impractical	Less expensive and practical
Data usage	Real data	Synthetic data can be used
Data capturing	Possible to capture behavioral factors that can disrupt the network	Some qualitative factors are difficult to simulate
Accuracy	High	Subject to assumptions
Major research approach	Mainly empirical approaches	Mainly modelling approaches

The collected data using empirical approaches can be analyzed using descriptive analytics in order to address the question “*what happened (or is happening)*”. However, some extreme conditions, which are impossible or expensive to test in actual environments can be integrated with optimization and simulation methods to generate predictive (i.e. to answer “*what will happen*”) and prescriptive (i.e. to answer “*what is the action plan*”) analytics (El Morr and Ali-Hassan 2019 p. 16-18, Jahani et al. 2023). Nevertheless, controlled settings can also be employed to predict scenarios and suggest possible recovery actions.

For practitioners, knowing what is currently happening inside the supply chain gives more realistic insights to prepare their contingency plans. Realizing different trajectories to the future

using the present conditions, provides companies a competitive edge among competitors while supporting business continuity plans. Moreover, knowing possible courses of actions in advance helps a business to take necessary actions for their recovery plans.

4.2. Usage of stress tests in practice

Stress testing using optimization and simulation models is becoming more popular due to their wide range of applications. We propose a framework connecting traditional and cognitive digital twin (i.e. intelligent digital twin (iDT)) to generalize the stress testing process in virtual environments, following the guidelines proposed by Ivanov (2023a).

Fig. 5 illustrates the process of integrating different risk data with stress testing models to generate mitigation plans. External and internal risk data are collected from sources such as sensors, smart devices, and social networks. These data are subsequently processed by cognitive systems and models, enabling self-learning, reasoning, the adjustment of decision-making rules, and stress testing. The proactive and reactive plans are developed accordingly.

Fig. 5. Supply chain stress testing framework using iDT

The understanding of various disruption scenarios for stress testing, as analyzed under section 3.4, can be integrated with the digital twin concept to develop generalized methodological guidelines that facilitate the decision-making process. Major five steps of the generalized guidelines are illustrated in Fig. 6.

Fig. 6. Generalized, digital twin-based methodological guidelines for stress testing (adopted with changes from Ivanov (2023a))

The real world physical supply chain is replicated in a virtual environment as the first step. The level of detail in the supply chain mapping directly influences the accuracy of the stress test. In the second step, disruptions are detected proactively and reactively using internal and external data. The vulnerable stakeholders are identified at this stage. Disruption modeling and visualization are carried out in the third step. The stress absorption level of the vulnerable stakeholders with available resources is prioritized and tested at this stage. Suitable KPIs are

selected for data visualization. Decisions are made in the fourth step. Decisions can be made during the pre-disruption, disruption, and post-disruption phases, aligned with resilience management strategies and the corresponding stage of analysis (Ivanov 2023a). Improving decision-making rules while generating disruption and resilience management knowledge for further development and training is the main focus of the fifth step.

4.3. Drivers for stress tests

Due to recent global developments, stress tests for SCR have become more critical than ever. Several drivers can be found in the literature (see Table 6) that practitioners should continuously assess to adjust their business continuity plans. We benchmarked the period after COVID-19 pandemic to find more recent drivers for stress testing.

Table 6. Visible drivers for stress testing in recent studies

	Major driver	Number of studies	Indicative references
Disruption	COVID-19	12	Raassens et al. (2021), Ivanov (2021b), Hosseini and Ivanov (2021), Sawik (2022)
	Natural hazards	3	Giannoccaro and Iftikhar (2020), Padhi and Mukherjee (2022), Bag et al. (2022)
	Internal and external disturbances	2	Hosseini and Ivanov (2022), Liu and Ren (2024)
Digitalization		4	Badakhshan and Ball (2022), Ambrogio et al. (2022), Brintrup et al. (2023), Padhi et al. (2024)
Strategic adaptation		2	Sakib et al. (2021), Park et al. (2021)

As expected, COVID-19 is the main driver in stress test related studies. Pandemic-like events are categorized as deep disruption events (i.e. unknown-unknown uncertainty). In other words, what and when something could happen is extremely hard to predict. Moreover, the stress level such events produce is higher and uncertain. Therefore, using different stress tests, practitioners can develop different resilience and viable capabilities to mitigate the impact. Natural hazards are the second most discussed aspect. Natural hazards are not rare events; however, their frequency and magnitude continue to increase. Natural hazards can range from random (i.e. known-known uncertainty) to hazard disruptions (i.e. known-unknown uncertainty) (Ivanov 2021a p. 11, Ivanov 2024). Although the stress level such events can inject is relatively low due to their predictability, their impact can disrupt the supply chain for extended periods. Other internal and external disturbances such as production disruptions caused by machine breakdowns and labor strikes, political decisions, and policy shifts (Liu and Ren 2024), can disrupt the usual operations while creating the ripple effect (Hosseini and Ivanov 2022).

The application of digital technologies is becoming an effective way to manage and improve supply chain performance. In particular, AI-based approaches such as ML (Badakhshan and Ball 2022, Brintrup et al. 2023) have the ability to find “complex relationships and hidden patterns” within large datasets (Ni et al. 2019), thereby facilitating the generation of accurate

predictions. Additionally, Digital Twin (Ambrogio et al. 2022) and Industry 4.0 (Padhi et al. 2024) conceptualize new ways of approaching supply chain disruptions.

Strategic adaptations are vital organizational moves in terms of resilience and viability. Closed-loop supply chain networks (Park et al. 2021) and collaborative intertwined supply chain networks (Sakib et al. 2021) for instance can be employed as mitigation strategies. On the contrary, such complex networks can bring additional disruptions to the system. Stress tests are imperative in this regard to understand to what extent such complexities should be integrated with the networks.

4.4. Future research directions

The wide range of applicability of the stress tests and the integration of new technologies create several future research avenues.

Stress tests and supply chain viability

Stress tests' ability to analyze complex supply chain networks creates several future research opportunities. The recently introduced concept of supply chain viability emphasizes adapting to changing environments and sustaining the supply chain as an open system (i.e. "bounce-forward-and-adapt") (Ivanov 2024). He further explains, the viable supply chains are often interconnected, creating intertwined supply chain networks with complex relationships among companies that "share common nodes and links". Analyzing changing environments and testing suitable intertwined network iterations can become extremely complicated. The COVID-19 pandemic, in particular, has demonstrated how a single event can introduce multiple stressors throughout the supply chain, each affecting it to different degrees. However, it is not realistic to expect the same event with the same stressors. Therefore, innovative ways of utilizing stress tests from different perspectives for various stressors are needed.

Key performance indicators

Several KPIs are constantly studied in the literature. Financial performance indicators (e.g. revenue, costs, profit) (Ivanov 2017a, Ivanov 2017b, Hosseini and Ivanov 2021, Badakhshan and Ball 2022, Sawik, 2023a), inventory (Ivanov 2017a, Ivanov 2017b, Park et al. 2021, Badakhshan and Ball 2022), and service level (Ivanov 2017a, Ivanov 2017b, Sawik, 2023a) are common indicators among others. However, when designing and implementing supply chain strategies for resilience and viability, more relevant indicators are imperative. Resilience (Moosavi and Hosseini 2021, Hosseini and Ivanov 2022), time-to-survive, time-to-recovery, and time-to-adapt (Ivanov 2023c) are a few emerging indicators that can be used and analyzed in the future studies.

Stress testing methods

While several methodologies are popular among researchers, others are underexplored. Recent advancements in the AI industry offer numerous opportunities for researchers and practitioners to explore the potential applications of methods such as metaheuristics, ML, and agent-based simulation to assess stresses induced by various disruption events. Additionally, simulation methods such as Monte-Carlo simulation, Markov chains, and regression can also be considered to analyze the problems from different perspectives. Application of the experimental approach is lacking in terms of empirical research.

Industry 5.0

The focus of Industry 5.0 is to integrate “viability, sustainability, human-centricity, and resilience” (Ivanov 2023d). The concept encompasses the supply chain operations in both the short and long run, considering environmental, economic and, human-centric factors. Six enabling technologies including bio-inspired technologies, digital twins and simulation, and AI are considered in Industry 5.0 (Xu et al., 2021). In the context of stress testing, growth in both the modelling and empirical methods are required. While the most optimum ways to interconnect industry 5.0 characteristics can be analyzed using modelling methods, the influence of qualitative factors including employee satisfaction, employee commitment, and corporate culture, which can lead to supply chain disruption can be examined employing empirical methods.

5. Conclusions

Supply chain networks are constantly stressed by internal and external disruptions to different degrees. Deep complex network structures make it harder for practitioners to understand what is happening inside the system to make accurate decisions. The COVID-19 pandemic provided an opportunity for companies to assess the effectiveness of their resilience strategies. Unfortunately, due to the absence of actively managed resilience capabilities, most supply chains were unable to withstand the constant stress. Meanwhile, the key questions raised in both academia and industry were: which resilience capabilities should be integrated into the system, to what extent, and at what point, in order to maintain operations while minimizing costs. Coined by Simchi-Levi and Simchi-Levi in 2020, stress tests can help address all of the aforementioned questions. However, to the best of our knowledge, no published research explicitly defines stress tests or analyzes related topics and methodologies.

In this paper, we analyzed the employment of stress tests in SCM. First, we analyzed the scope and the application of stress test in other fields including medicine, social science, and finance, and defined the term with respect to SCM. Second, we performed a bibliometric analysis to find trending topics, commonly applied methodologies, and analyzed disruption areas. Finally, the theoretical and managerial implications were derived.

The major findings of our study can be elaborated as follows. Although several studies use the term "stress test," a precise definition has yet to be established. Therefore, we provide a definition from the SCM perspective to clarify and distinguish its intended meaning. We identified different methodologies applied in the literature and categorized them according to their applications. The ways in which managers can utilize different stress tests to understand past (what has happened) or ongoing (what is happening) system behaviors, predict various scenarios, and manage resilience capabilities were explained. A novel digital twin framework was introduced as an approach to conduct stress tests in virtual environments, followed by generalized digital twin-based methodological guidelines for stress testing. Finally, we identified the key drivers for stress tests based on recent studies from our sample. This led us to outline several promising research directions for future works.

Finally, we would like to highlight that supply chains are constantly stressed by numerous internal and external, predictable and unpredictable, controllable and uncontrollable disruption events. Without proper stress tests to analyze potential scenarios, most supply chains are likely

to fail. Investments for resilience and viability can be expensive if they do not provide returns. Therefore, identifying the correct set of capabilities and maintaining them is imperative. In this setting, stress testing can not only analyze current performance and predict future outcomes but also recommend different combinations of capabilities to ensure the continuity of the supply chain.

Data Availability Statement

Data related with this paper is available with authors and will be available upon reasonable request.

Conflict of Interest

No conflict of interest has to be declared.

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Appendix 2

Appendix 3

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Reference	Major problem	Methodology	Application	Stress test analysis		
				Parameters	KPIs	Recommendations
Trkman and McCormack 2009	How to assess the suppliers' disruption risk depending on their strategy, structure, performance, and attributes?	Case-study	To assess the risk levels of different suppliers and manage it at disruptions.	Performance turbulence of suppliers	Turbulence index	Non-performing suppliers should be closely monitored and if possible replaced.
Mizgier et al. 2013	How to identify firms that induce high losses due to disruptions to the focal firm and the entire supply chain?	Monte Carlo simulation	The model can be used as an efficient tool for the quantification of losses due to supply chain disruptions from single suppliers, both in isolation and when embedded in the network structure.	Changing corresponding intensities (days) of each node	Loss of daily turnover	Supply chain reconfiguration
Ivanov et al. 2014	How to integrate aggregate distribution and dynamic transportation planning simultaneously in the context of supply chains under capacity disruptions?	Linear programming	The model can particularly be used by logistics service providers to improve the integrated planning at capacity disruptions with disruption propagation.	Transportation and facility capacity unavailability	Service level	-
Bode and Wagner, 2015	How do the structural characteristics of supply chains affect the frequency of disruptions experienced by buying firms?	Survey research	To design their supply chains that are more disruption-prone, using observable supply chain characteristics such as the number of direct suppliers or the geographic distances between a focal firm and its suppliers.	Frequency of suppliers unavailability	Supply chain complexity	Supply chain simplification (within the limits of business model)
Sokolov et al. 2015	How to analyze the impact of the disruptions on the supply chain performance (i.e. cost and service level) according to structural characteristics?	Graph theory	To estimate both dynamic performance (i.e. cost and service level) and static structural characteristics, such as robustness, flexibility, resilience, centralization,	Partial unavailability of different nodes and arcs	Robustness Resilience Flexibility Efficiency	Supply chain redesign

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			and complexity when the ripple effect presents.		Centralization Production and transportation costs Service level On-time delivery	
Dixit et al. 2016	How to analyze the resilience of the supply chain network considering trade-offs?	Multi-objective stochastic mixed-integer programming	To understand the behavior of service level/unfulfilled demand and total transportation cost at different external disturbances in the post-disaster stage.	Variance of the capacity of the network	Unfulfilled demand Transportation cost	-
Ivanov et al. 2016a	How to re-plan the material flow when the supply chain is disrupted under different extents and at different times?	Hybrid of system dynamics and linear programming	To understand the resilience level of the existing supply chain and make changes to the design accordingly.	Nodes (facilities) and arcs (channels) are unavailable for different durations	Service level Sales/Revenue Costs	The resilience level of the network should be measured under uncertain disruption scenarios for optimal reconfiguration.
Ivanov et al. 2016b	How to quantify the structural reliability to identify a group of suppliers, which interrupts the SC operations?	Graph theory	To consider different supply chain configurations to improve reliability when critical suppliers are disrupted.	Unavailability of nodes and arcs	Reliability Costs	Supply chain reconfiguration
Ivanov et al. 2016c	How to optimize the recovery policies in case of time-critical supply chains (e.g. highly perishable products) at ripple effect?	Discrete-event simulation	To estimate the impact of possible perturbations on economic performance at the SC design and inventory planning stage.	Unavailability of distribution center	Sales/Revenues Costs Profits	Appropriate recovery policies can mitigate the stress placed by disruptions.
Ivanov, 2017a	How to analyze supply chain dynamic changes caused by the ripple effect	Discrete-event simulation	To study disruption propagation caused by capacity disruptions in a	Variance of warehouse capacity	Sales/Revenues Costs	An increase in safety stock at the downstream

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	using complex simulation models?		complex multi-echelon supply chain network.		Service level	facilities can prevent disruption propagation.
Ivanov, 2017b	What sustainability factors mitigate and enhance the ripple effect in the supply chain?	Discrete-event simulation	To analyze three different mitigation strategies (i.e. sourcing policy, facility fortification, reduction in storage facilities) against disruptions to improve resilience and sustainability.	Unavailability of primary distribution center	Service level	Backup facilities should be integrated in case of severe and lengthy disruptions.
Ivanov et al. 2017a	How to adjust the production schedule as a reaction to recovering from severe disruptions in supply chain capacities?	Control theory	To assess the resilience level of the supply chain at different disruption scenarios and prepare if needed using mitigation strategies such as reconfiguration.	Full or partial unavailability of facility capacities	Resilience	Supply chain reconfiguration
Ivanov et al. 2017b	How to incorporate return material flows, disruptions duration, and capacity recovery costs into supply chain design, planning, control decisions, and performance impact assessment?	Hybrid of linear programming and system dynamics model	To identify the most profitable recovery view while comparing with the service level achieved in different periods and for different recovery policies.	Partial or full unavailability of capacities	Sales/Revenues Service level Costs	-
Paul et al. 2017	How to revise the supply chain plan to minimize the losses due to demand fluctuations and production disruptions?	Fuzzy inference system	To predict the demand using demand fluctuations, unexpected incidents, and natural incidents data to make quantitative decisions (i.e. predictive mitigations) and to decide necessary actions to be taken at production disruptions that cannot be predicted in advance (i.e. reactive mitigations).	Inoperability of production plants Loss of production quantity	Costs	The supply chain plan should be revised after any sudden disruptions that cannot be predicted in advance, on a real-time basis to mitigate the effects.

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Gunessee et al. 2018	How to moderate (i.e. mitigate) the effect of natural disasters that can change corporate performance?	Experimental research	The analysis proves that catastrophic vulnerability (i.e. natural disasters) can affect enterprises short and long term and enterprises should constantly study and analyze previous disruption events to prepare the supply chain for future disaster events.	Fluctuations of sales ratio (sales-to-assets)	-	Fluctuations should be analyzed constantly and integrated with the system as learnings for future events.
Ivanov et al. 2018	How the digitalization and Industry 4.0 impact on the ripple effect and disruption risk control analytics in the supply chain?	Case-study	To understand the interrelationship between SCM, digitalization, and risk propagation, and important steps to use such solutions as decision support systems.	-	-	-
Ojha et al. 2018	How to quantify the exposed risk and measure resilience at risk propagation?	Bayesian network model	To quantify the exposed risk facility-wise (manufacturing, distribution) prior to and after the risk mitigation strategies using risk exposure indices.	Nodes (facilities) are unavailable for different durations	Fragility Service level Inventory & backup cost Lost sales	Tedious and costly supply chain proactive measures should be assigned to the facilities with high-risk exposure. Reduce dependency on the finished goods inventory.
Pavlov et al. 2018	How to identify the impact of disruptions on SCR at different locations of the chain and find critical nodes?	Hybrid fuzzy-probabilistic approach	To assess the resilience level of the supply chain for different disruption scenarios and to find suitable reconfigurations to mitigate the disruption effects.	Unavailability of vertices and edges	Resilience	At disruptions, both proactive and reactive policies should be included to get a fair resilience estimation that can be compared with different supply chain designs.

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Wang et al. 2018	How to improve SCR using intertwined supply chain networks?	Petri nets	To predict the disruptions (early warning system) in an intertwined network to develop proactive resilience strategies.	Variations of parameters: demand, production plan, component availability (Using random functions)	Utilization of production capacity Unsatisfied demand Inventory level Products sold Relationship with suppliers Operating time saved	Resource-rich members should share redundancies with resource-needy members to prevent the disruption propagation.
Hosseini et al. 2019	How and when to use both proactive and reactive strategies in supplier selection and order allocation?	Stochastic bi-objective mixed integer programming	To design supply networks that minimize not only traditional supply costs but also possible losses due to disruptive risks while increasing SCR using different absorptive, adaptive, and restorative capabilities.	Disrupted suppliers	Costs Segregation distance	Supplier selection and restoration costs and suppliers' distance should be compared when selecting optimal supplier selection policy
López and Ishizaka 2019	How to improve the SCR by accurate outsourcing location decisions?	Fuzzy cognitive maps and analytic hierarchy process	To evaluate the alternative outsourcing locations according to their impact on SCR.	Fluctuations of sixteen variables including five trigger variables (i.e. transport infrastructure, political risks, tax rates, technological infrastructure, and exchange rates)	Resilience	Positive and negative intensities of variables that stress the network should be assessed to predict the accurate outsourcing location decision with higher resilience.
Rahmani and Yavari 2019	How to optimize the pricing and production policies	Stackelberg game	To find the break-even point of changing the production and pricing	Fluctuation of demand	Profit	Adjusting the green degree and the

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	when demand disruptions occur in a green supply chain?		policies depending on the severity of the demand disruptions.		Production quantity Green degree	production quantity is necessary when the demand disruption exceeds the threshold. The central decision maker should always revise the original decisions when a demand disruption occurs.
Giannoccaro and Iftikhar 2020	How does trust interact with the supply chain topology to affect supply network resilience?	Agent-based model	To find possible network topologies to stay resilient at disruption propagation based on the developed trust between partners.	Fluctuations of network performance	Resilience	Network-level trust can enhance the resilience of the network.
Padhi and Mukherjee 2022	How to split the supply orders under supply disruptions due to natural disasters?	Survey research	To identify the optimal quantities to order from primary and backup suppliers under disruptions in order to maintain long-term relationships with both parties.	Unavailability of suppliers during a particular period	-	During the disruption period, the order quantity should be revised and split between backup and primary suppliers without damaging the long-term relationship with the primary supplier.
Ghadge et al. 2021	How to capture the impact of disruption propagation of both individual and multiple simultaneous risks on	System dynamic approach	The scenario-based simulation analysis can be used to picture the supply chain disruption propagation phenomenon from macro and micro-level perspectives.	Variations and discrepancies in variables	Demand Transport capacity Supply	-

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	different supply chain nodes?					
Hosseini and Ivanov 2021	How to simulate and quantify the impact of supply chain disruptions in the wake of a pandemic using disruption triggers and risk events?	Bayesian network model	To simulate and quantify the impact of unforeseen disruption triggers on supply chain operations and performance (i.e. lead-time increase, service level decrease, and lost sales).	Probabilistic disruptions of nodes	Lost sales	Multiple sourcing and decentralized systems can potentially reduce the stress placed by the disruptions.
Ivanov 2021b	How can the firms avoid negative consequences of the disruption tails and associated after-shock risks when exiting the pandemic?	Discrete-event simulation	The model can be used by managers to analyze the risk of disruption tails in their supply chains and guide the selection of post-pandemic recovery strategies.	Fluctuations of demand	Service level On-time delivery Daily inventory average	Supply chain coordination by means of demand smoothing. Gradual capacity ramp-up to control disruption tails.
Moosavi and Hosseini 2021	What is the impact of resilience strategies (i.e. prepositioning extra inventory and a backup supplier) in a multi-stage SC in the presence of a pandemic?	Discrete-event simulation	To develop a response plan in the occurrence of a pandemic or any long-duration high magnitude disruption.	Unavailability of supplier Production line stop	Profit Sales/Revenues Costs Resilience Demand fulfillment	Resilience focused supply chains should integrate excess inventory during the disruptions while financial focused should integrate backup suppliers
Park et al. 2021	How do circular supply chain structures impact both the ripple effect of supply chain disruptions and the supply chain's resilience?	Discrete-event simulation	To assess the importance of knowing directly and indirectly connected supply networks to mitigate the risk of disruption ripple effects by adjusting safety stock or overproduction capabilities in a circular flow.	Reduction of production rate	Backlogged period Recovery period Robustness	Analyze the structure of the supply network beyond the second tiers and adjust the safety stock or overproduction capacities accordingly.

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Raassens et al. 2021	How does COVID-19 impact the food service supply chain, and what crisis management strategies firms can use during such disruptions to survive?	Survey research	This empirical approach can be used to learn lessons from current disruptions and prepare the supply chain network for the future by maintaining long-term relationships with partners and reducing social distance.	Unavailability of goods during COVID-19	-	Resource management, resource dependency, collaboration, and effective communication.
Sakib et al. 2021	How to predict and assess disasters based on several factors including technical, economic, social, political, safety, environmental, and legal to mitigate their effects?	Bayesian network model	The disruption assessment model can be used to assess the probabilistic disaster, which in turn will be valuable for disaster preparedness.	Probabilistic disruptions of nodes	-	-
Ambrogio et al. 2022	How can manufacturing firms cope with urgent staff deficiencies while sustaining them at the same time?	Case-study	To enhance the future of industrial work and the safety levels at workplaces using technology-driven solutions such as Plug-and-play workers, remote operators 4.0 and, healthy operator 4.0.	Unavailability of workforce	-	Digital toolbox (i.e. plug-and-play worker, remote operator 4.0 and healthy operator 4.0) can considerably improve the robustness and resilience of the industrial workforce.
Badakhshan and Ball 2022	How can a supply chain digital twin help in identifying the inventory and cash replenishment policies that mitigate the impact of the disruptions?	Discrete-event simulation	The model can be integrated with ML algorithms, which could establish a set of decision rules for setting inventory and cash replenishment policies to minimize the impact of disruptions.	Increment of credit purchase policies Increasing demand and decreasing	Cash conversion cycle Service level Inventory levels Production levels	-

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				production capacity		
Bag et al. 2022	How do big data and predictive analytics capabilities affect supply chain visibility, community, and resource resilience?	Survey research	The finding can be used as a guidance to build resources and community resilience, which can mitigate the negative impacts on the communities	Supply chain visibility at pre, during, and post-extreme weather events	Resilience	Big data and predictive analytics capabilities can improve companies' ability to make the best use of there available resources.
Hosseini and Ivanov 2022	How to quantify the SCR of the original equipment manufacturer with a multi-stage assessment of suppliers' proneness to disruptions and the supply chain exposure to the ripple effect?	Bayesian network model	To identify the disruption profiles in the supply base and associated supply chain performance degradation due to the ripple effect.	Probabilistic disruptions of nodes	Resilience	The resilience should be quantified to re-design the supply base.
Ivanov 2022	What are research-practice paradoxes stemming from typical problem settings and assumptions in SCR and viability modelling?	Case (paradoxes) study	The concepts can be used to raise the awareness of understanding different paradoxes related to resilience and viability for optimal strategizing.	-	-	-
Küffner et al. 2022	What measures purchasing and supply management can implement over time to increase SCR?	Survey research	To compare existing response measures and develop strategies on how the purchasing and supply management should respond to major disruptions.	Fluctuations of suppliers' capacity during long-term crises	-	Initial measures (e.g. communication and coordination), temporary measures (e.g. trust-based relationships) and, post-disruption

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						measures (e.g. multiple sourcing) are essential to mitigate disruptions.
Sawik 2022	Are typical resilience measures effective means for the supply chains to survive and recover through the pandemic-like disruption propagations?	Stochastic optimization	The analysis can be used as a comprehensive decision-making model for the optimization of global supply chain operations under pandemic-like disruptions, risks, and ripple effect.	Probabilistic disruptions of duration, available capacity, order fulfillment rate. Random changes in demand	Costs Service level	Employing risk mitigation inventory and backup suppliers against disruptions to improve resilience.
Brintrup et al. 2023	What is digital supply chain surveillance and the role of AI in it?	Survey research and case-study	To improve proactive monitoring, managing, and analyzing activities, which can lead to better end-to-end visibility.	-	-	-
Sawik 2023a	How to maintain the supply chain viability under ripple effect using two conflicting objectives (i.e. cost-optimal and service-optimal)?	Stochastic optimization	For decision makers to improve the resilience and viability under severe disruptions by changing the boundaries.	Unavailability of nodes	Costs Service level	Disruption mitigation and viability can be established using backup supplies, capacity reservation and pre-positioned risk mitigation inventory.
Sawik 2023b	How to reshore to domestic regions optimally with minimum risk under ripple effect?	Stochastic mixed integer programming	The model allows the decision makers to evaluate the operational impact of the strategic decision under disruption propagation.	Introducing disruption levels to supply chain nodes	Expected cost/expected service level	Reshoring the supply chain can better satisfy the market demand during disruptions.

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					Cost-at-risk/ service-at-risk"	
Liu and Ren 2024	How the production disruptions (caused by the breakdown of equipment, labor strike or, natural disaster) impact the consumer, supply chain agents, and society?	Mean-variance method	To make optimum decisions and to assess the performance at production disruptions in both centralized and decentralized supply chain structures.	Level of production disruption	Profit	Setting a lower retail price when disruptions are highly possible.
Liu et al. 2024	How to analyze worst-case oriented disruption risk assessment under the ripple effect for multi-echelon supply chains?	Robust dynamic Bayesian network model	The disrupted manufacturer can acquire a robust risk estimation.	Probabilistic disruptions of nodes	-	Budget deviations can be controlled to alter the manufacturers' risk during disruptions.
Padhi et al. 2024	How do risk-averse firm's investment decisions affect its adoption of Industry 4.0 technologies?	Survey research	To deal with Industry 4.0-related investment decisions that can address the supply chain risks in different stages of implementation.	-	-	-